

Exoskeletons - Challenges for Occupational Safety and Health

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Abstract: Overuse injuries caused by manual material handling tasks (MMH) is still a common problem in workplaces worldwide. At present exoskeletons are being mentioned more frequently to address this problem. The new body-worn technology is designed to reduce physical stress during working tasks and should prevent work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs). Even though exoskeletons have reached market maturity many questions with regard to occupational safety and health remain to be answered. Due to the variety of applications and types of exoskeletons no uniform definition exists. This raises new questions concerning regulations and certifications of exoskeletons as they can currently be used as a technical aid, personal protective equipment (PPE), medical device or sports equipment. In addition, the health effects of exoskeletons on human physiology and their prevention from WRMSDs are still poorly understood. There is currently a lack of practice-orientated studies that consider health related questions of exoskeletons over a long period of time. Nevertheless exoskeletons can provide a promising approach to support workers during their daily tasks and prevent from WRMSDs. The article summarises the results of the EU-OSHA discussion paper on the impact of Exoskeletons on Occupational Safety and Health [1].

Keywords: Exoskeletons, Occupational Safety and Health, WRMSD, MMH, Risk assessment

1 Introduction

In Europe over 40 % of the working population still suffering from musculoskeletal complaints, which frequently affects the spine, shoulders and neck [2]. These issues are related to repetitive working tasks or potentially hazardous body postures during MMH, which includes lifting, lowering, carrying and holding loads [3]. The costs for the health care system are estimated at 2 % of Europe's gross domestic product [4] and consequently have economic relevance. The need for ergonomic tools to address this problem, especially when considering demographic aspects, is high. Recently exoskeletons were introduced for a wide range of applications to protect workers from overuse injuries. Although the idea to support human movements with exoskeletons has been there for several decades, their application at workplaces to protect workers from WRMSDs, is new.

Exoskeletons are personal assistance devices that affect the body with mechanical support [5]. Due to their variety concerning type, functionality and application, there is no common definition in the literature until today, but there is a basic agreement, describing them as on-body external mechanical structures [6, 7]. Exoskeletons support human muscle strength or modify external force effects on the body

to reduce physical stress. A distinction can be made between passive and active systems. Active Systems use hydraulic or pneumatic driven mechanisms or electrical actuators (drive units) [8] to increase the performance of the user. Passive exoskeletons, on the other hand, use springs and dampers to store and release energy harvested by the movements of the user [7]. Exoskeletons are already being tested at workplaces worldwide in order to gain new findings on practical suitability. Nevertheless, their application raises new questions concerning occupational safety and health issues.

2 Fields of Application

Exoskeletons have been developed for military purposes for some time and are used with modified functionality in medical care as orthoses for rehabilitative purposes to restore physical health of patients. However, in Europe 30 % of daily working tasks are related to MMH [2]. Many of these tasks involve carrying heavy loads that can imply a high health risk to the musculoskeletal system. Thus, exoskeletons are likely to have the potential to assist in many working tasks to reduce physical stress.

Their support could be used in medical care to facilitate the lifting of patients or to assist firefighters in their tasks. Furthermore the use of exoskeletons at

industrial workplaces is also conceivable. In addition to the commercial applications there is also an interest for private purposes. Some manufacturers offer exoskeletons as sports equipment to reduce muscle fatigue.

Nevertheless, it must be taken into account that ergonomic design is the first priority to improve working conditions. Especially stationary workplaces do offer the opportunity for a human centred design and therefore enhance working processes or reduce physical strain of workers. Thus exoskeletons should not be used as long as measures provide the possibility of a better ergonomic design [9]. Exoskeletons offer great potential improving working conditions at non-stationary workplaces where ergonomic measures are difficult to implement e.g. furniture delivery services or hospitals. Yet the increase in performance due to exoskeletons seems to be of greater interest than the potential benefits of health care aspects [10]. Therefore they are currently the subject of controversial discussions in the literature.

Depending on the intended use of exoskeletons and their functional design, different regulations have to be considered which in turn have an influence on their practical application. As long as they are used to facilitate the working process passive and active exoskeletons can be described as technical aids according to the European Machinery Directive [11]. The regulations of robots and robotic devices as well as the safety requirements for personal care robots can be used to specify active systems [12, 13]. If exoskeletons are used to reduce physical stress of workers and prevent from WRMSDs they can be classified as PPE according to the new European regulation 2016/425 [14]. In terms of reintegration management or rehabilitation proposes exoskeletons have to be considered as medical products in regard to the European directive 93/42/EEC [15].

Besides the intended use of exoskeletons, employers have the general duty to ensure safety and health at work [16]. In the context of risk assessment product safety of exoskeletons is a basic prerequisite. New technologies also involve new risks that have to be considered. Thus malfunctions that could lead to a health risk must be excluded. In the event of a slip, trip or fall incident additional or more serious injuries may occur and should be prevented. In the case of an emergency, or emergency evacuation, further risks could arise.

Until today the practical application of exoskeletons and the risks involved can only be roughly presented in user scenarios due to the lack of experience.

3 Evaluation of Exoskeletons

In recent years several investigations have been performed to evaluate exoskeletons. In particular, the effects of exoskeletons on human biomechanics and physiology were subject of research. In addition, user acceptance is important and is also frequently mentioned in literature. As already mentioned, their advantages and disadvantages are currently the subject of controversial debate.

External structures such as exoskeletons attached to the body do not only have positive effects. Although this is strongly dependent on type of exoskeleton, it is mentioned in literature, that the additional weight of an exoskeleton possibly increases oxygen demands [17]. In contrast Whitfield et al. [18] detected no increased oxygen consumption using an ergonomic lifting aid. Regardless of support, the author admitted not to increase the workload with the ergonomic tool. Also sex, walking speed and Body-weight have an impact on the oxygen consumption rate [19].

Biomechanical impacts have already been investigated in many ways and repeatedly show similar conclusions. Accordingly, it was demonstrated that the physical stress in single joints can be reduced by exoskeletons [7, 17, 20, 21]. At the same time loads are redistributed to other biological structures where the long-term effects are difficult to predict. Moreover, it is likely that altered movement patterns occur due to movement limitations or due to the additional weight added by the exoskeleton. The results of biomechanical research are important to understand mechanical effects of exoskeletons on the human body, but for now they cannot be used for practical recommendations.

User acceptance is a main aspect when designing exoskeletons. Acceptability depends in many cases on subjective rating such as comfort or design but also functionality, since exoskeletons are currently developed for a specific use case and can be less effective in other working tasks. Hensel et al. [22] describes a decreasing acceptance over time what is possibly related to comfort and usability. Also aspects of stigmatisation can reduce the acceptability, as exoskeletons may be associated with muscular debility.

4 Summary

Currently the topic of exoskeletons receives a lot of attention. Although the practical application of exoskeletons for specific working tasks seems to provide

a promising approach in future, their wide application at workplaces can be questioned. At present only little scientific evidence exists, especially long-term effects of exoskeletons are poorly understood. However, the ergonomic design of workplaces should always be the first approach to improve working conditions and to prevent from WMSDs.

5 Literature

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